

Dynamics of Large Systems of Identical Oscillators with Delayed Couplings of Advective Type

Elena V. Grigorieva*

*Department of Mathematics, Belarus State Economical University,
26 Partizansky Ave., 220070 Minsk, Republic of Belarus*

Dmitriy S. Kashchenko

P. G. Demidov Yaroslavl State University, 14 Sovetskaya Ave., 150003 Yaroslavl, RUSSIA

Sergey A. Kashchenko and Anna O. Tolbey

*Regional Scientific and Educational Mathematical Center of Integrable Systems,
P. G. Demidov Yaroslavl State University, 14 Sovetskaya Ave., 150003 Yaroslavl, RUSSIA*

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Local dynamics of a large number of identical oscillators is investigated. Instead of a system of coupled equations, a single partial integro-differential equation is proposed which can model the chain with coupling lines of advective type and takes into account large delay time in coupling lines. We show that asymptotically infinite number of modes are excited at the critical conditions when zero equilibrium state becomes unstable. The special nonlinear boundary value problems of the parabolic type are derived which play a role of the quasi-normal forms in the cases of bi- and unidirectional couplings, for weak and strong dissipation of the oscillators, for distributed and discrete couplings, for odd and even numbers of the oscillators. The nonlocal dynamics of each quasi-normal form describes the behavior of the main terms of the asymptotic expansions of nonlinear solutions of the original problem.

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1. Introduction

as

First, let us consider a model of the ring of N coupled oscillators,

$$f(u, \dot{u}) = b_1 u^3 + b_2 u^2 \dot{u} + b_3 u \dot{u}^2 + b_4 \dot{u}^3 + o(|u|^4), \quad (2)$$

$$\ddot{u}_j + a \dot{u}_j + u + f(u, \dot{u}) = d \sum_{k=1}^N \psi_k u_k(t - T), \quad (1)$$

where $j = 1, 2, \dots$, $u_j \equiv u_{j+N}$, $a > 0$ is the dissipation coefficient, $T > 0$ is the delay time, ψ_k are weight coefficients of the coupling level $d > 0$. The nonlinear function $f(u, \dot{u})$ in the neighborhood of the zero equilibrium state reads

where we omit quadratic nonlinear terms in order just to simplify the analysis presented below (without loss of generality).

Dynamical properties of such chains without delay have been studied by many authors, for example, in [1–3]. The delay-induced effects were studied in works [4–14]. Previously, the main attention was paid to chains with a small number of elements. Here we assume that the number N of chain elements is sufficiently large and we introduce the small parameter

*E-mail: grigorieva@tut.by.

$$\varepsilon = 2\pi N^{-1} \ll 1. \quad (3)$$

It is natural to associate the functions $u_j(t)$ with the values of a function of two variables $u(t, x_j)$, where x_j are angular values of points uniformly distributed on some circle: $x_j = 2\pi N^{-1}j = \varepsilon j$. Instead of the system (1) for $u(t, x_j)$, we propose to consider the equation for the function $u(t, x)$ of a continuous spatial variable $x \in (-\infty, \infty)$ and with the condition of 2π -periodicity,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + a \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u + f\left(u, \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}\right) = d \int_0^{2\pi} \Psi(s) u(t - T, x + s) ds, \quad (4)$$

$$u(t, x + 2\pi) \equiv u(t, x). \quad (5)$$

The expression for $\Psi(s)$ should be determined by the coefficients of ψ_k . In what follows, we propose to use, instead of the integral of $\Psi(s)$ on the interval $[0, 2\pi]$, the integral of $\Phi(s)$ over an infinite interval

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi(s) u(t - T, x + s) ds,$$

where $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$ and $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$ read as

$$\Phi_1(s) = F_\varepsilon(s) - F_{-\varepsilon}(s), \quad (6)$$

$$\Phi_2(s) = F_\varepsilon(s) - F_0(s), \quad (7)$$

$$F_0(s) = \frac{1}{\sigma\varepsilon\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2\varepsilon^2\sigma^2}\right),$$

$$F_{\pm\varepsilon}(s) = \frac{1}{\sigma\varepsilon\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{(s \mp \varepsilon)^2}{2\varepsilon^2\sigma^2}\right), \quad \sigma > 0.$$

These functions have some properties suitable for further analysis. The parameter σ in the formulas for $F(s, \varepsilon)$ determines a set of elements of the ring that significantly affect on each particular element. This action is weaker the farther the elements are from each other. At $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ the

following limits hold for each continuous and bounded function $v(x)$,

$$\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi_1(s) v(x + s) ds = v(x + \varepsilon) - v(x - \varepsilon), \quad (8)$$

$$\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi_2(s) v(x + s) ds = v(x + \varepsilon) - v(x), \quad (9)$$

i.e. at $\sigma \rightarrow 0$ the functions $\Phi_{1,2}(s)$ have essential value mainly in a small neighborhood of points $s = 0, s = \pm\varepsilon$, respectively. Thus, the coupling specified by the function $\Phi_1(s)$ can be characterized as bidirectional while the coupling given by the function $\Phi_2(s)$ can be characterized as unidirectional.

Note, the expressions in the right-hand sides of the limits (8), (9) usually arise, for example, when applying the standard difference approximation of the advection (transfer) operator $\partial v / \partial x$. Therefore, they can naturally model an advection-type couplings.

The functions (6), (7) are also convenient to use for linear analysis since they allow to express the following integral through the exponential functions,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F_{\pm}(s, \varepsilon) \exp(iks) ds = \exp(\pm ik\varepsilon) \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma^2 \varepsilon^2 k^2}{2}\right).$$

Distributed models similar to Eqs. (4), (5) were previously proposed to describe the dynamics of globally coupled ensembles [14], large chains with diffusion-type couplings [15], chains with unidirectional and bidirectional couplings [13, 16]. The dynamics of chains without taking into account the delay in coupling lines was studied in [17]. At the same time, it is known that delay can induce excitation of a number of modes when an equilibrium becomes unstable.

In this paper we suppose additionally that the delay time is sufficiently large,

$$T = c\varepsilon^{-1}, \quad (10)$$

where $c > 0$ is “delay” in ε units. Normalizing time variable t in Eq.(4) to Tt we get the equation

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + \varepsilon a \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u + f\left(u, \varepsilon \frac{\partial u}{\partial t}\right) \\ = d \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi(s) u(t - c, x + s) ds, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$u(t, x + 2\pi) \equiv u(t, x), \quad (12)$$

which we will analyze below. Note, that the degenerate equation (11) at $\varepsilon = 0$ does not give information about the behavior of solutions of the boundary value problem (11), (12) at small ε , hence special asymptotic methods have to be applied to analyze such a singularly perturbed boundary value problem as it was discussed in [21–24].

The standard way for investigating the behavior of solutions with initial conditions from some sufficiently small neighborhood of the zero equilibrium is based on the study of the corresponding linearized system. In the finite-dimensional critical case, when some of characteristic roots have zero real part, the method of invariant integral manifolds and the method of normal forms (see, e.g., [25, 26]) are applied to obtain nonlinear solution. In the problem under consideration, critical cases can be called infinite-dimensional since infinitely many roots of the characteristic equation tend to the imaginary axis at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, the methods of invariant integral manifolds and normal forms are not directly applicable. Here we will use the method developed in [18–20], in order to obtain infinite-dimensional quasinormal forms.

The material of the article is presented as follows. In Section 2 the critical parameters are found at which the zero equilibrium state becomes unstable. The asymptotic representation of all those roots of the characteristic equation whose real part tends to zero when the small parameter ε tends to zero is presented. Such roots turn out to be infinitely many. Euler solutions are obtained for the linearized problem.

In Section 3, the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) is studied at $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$. The solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem are represented as series on ε degrees, $u(t, x, \varepsilon) = \varepsilon U_1 + \varepsilon^3 U_3 + \dots$, where the main term of the series, εU_1 , is written as the general solution of the linearized problem with a slowly varying amplitude. The absence of quadratic terms follows from Eq.(2). The series term U_3 (like others) is periodic in several of its arguments and can be found through the first term of the series U_1 . The nonlinear analysis performed leads to the equation for the slow amplitude of U_1 which plays the role of a quasinormal form.

In Section 4 the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) is studied at $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$ and the corresponding quasinormal form is obtained.

In Section 5 we assume that the parameter σ is sufficiently small, $\sigma = \varepsilon \sigma_1$, and we find corresponding quasinormal forms as equations for the main slow amplitude depending on three spatial variables.

2. Linear analysis

We start with the linearized boundary value problem

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + \varepsilon a \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \\ = d \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \Phi(s) u(t - c, x + s) ds, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$u(t, x + 2\pi) \equiv u(t, x). \quad (14)$$

Putting $u \sim \exp(ikx + \lambda t)$ we get the characteristic equation

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon^2 \lambda^2 + \varepsilon a \lambda + 1 = dg(z) \exp(-\sigma^2 z^2 - \lambda c), \\ z = \varepsilon k, \quad k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where in the case of $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$ we have

$$g(z) = g_1(z) = 2i \sin z, \quad (16)$$

or, in the case of $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$ we have

$$g(z) = g_2(z) = \exp(iz) - 1. \quad (17)$$

If all roots of Eq.(15) at any $k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$ have negative real parts separated from zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, then the solutions of the boundary value problem (13), (14) are asymptotically stable, and the solutions of Eqs.(11), (12) with sufficiently small and independent of ε (by the norm $C_{[0,2\pi]} \times C(R^2)$) initial conditions tend to zero at $t \rightarrow \infty$. If Eq.(15) has a root with a positive and real part separated from zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, then the solutions of Eqs.(13), (14) are unstable and the dynamics problem (11), (12) becomes nonlocal.

Let us determine the minimal (critical) coupling level $d = d_0$ at which Eq.(15) has a root with zero or sufficiently closed to zero real part at some k . To this end we put $\lambda = i\omega\varepsilon^{-1}$ in Eq.(15), where ω is real value, and obtain the equation

$$1 - \omega^2 + i\omega = d\gamma(z), \quad (18)$$

where $z = \varepsilon k, k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$,

$$\gamma(z) = g(z) \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 z^2 - i\omega\varepsilon^{-1}\right).$$

Denote by $P(\omega)$ the polynomial in the left part of Eq.(18) and by $p(\omega)$ and $\Omega(\omega)$ its modulus and phase,

$$P(\omega) = 1 - \omega^2 + i\omega = p(\omega) \exp(i\Omega(\omega)),$$

$$p(\omega) = [(1 - \omega^2)^2 + a^2\omega^2]^{1/2}.$$

Let

$$p_0 = \min_{-\infty < \omega < \infty} p(\omega) = p(\omega_0), \quad \Omega_0 = \Omega(\omega_0).$$

Here

$$\omega_0 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } a^2 \geq 2, \\ \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2}\right)^{1/2}, & \text{if } a^2 < 2, \end{cases}$$

$$p_0 = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } a^2 \geq 2, \\ \frac{a^2}{2}(4 - a^2)^{1/2}, & \text{if } a^2 < 2 \end{cases}$$

and $p_0 = 0$ at $a = 0$.

Remark. In what follows we will distinguish the oscillator models with weak dissipation $a^2 < 2$ or strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$.

Evidently, Eq.(18) has no real roots at each fixed z if $d|\gamma(z)| < p_0$. Let us denote

$$|\gamma_0| = \max_{-\infty < z < \infty} |\gamma(z)| = |\gamma(z_0)|. \quad (19)$$

If $d|\gamma_0| < p_0$ and ε is sufficiently small, all roots of Eq.(15) have negative and real parts separated from zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. If $d|\gamma_0| > p_0$, there is such z_0 that Eq.(15) has a root with a positive and separated from zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ real part. The critical value of the the coupling level, at which the equilibrium state of Eqs.(13), (14) becomes unstable, satisfies the equality

$$d_0 = p_0|\gamma_0|^{-1}.$$

Let us find the corresponding z_0 value using the condition $\gamma'(z_0) = 0$. For the model with bidirectional couplings specified by the function $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$ and $g(z) = g_1(z)$ given by Eq.(16) we find that the value of z_0 is the first positive root of the equation

$$\operatorname{tg} z = 2(\sigma^2 z)^{-1}. \quad (20)$$

For the model with unidirectional couplings specified by the function $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$ and $g(z) = g_2(z)$ given by Eq.(17) we find that the value of z_0 is the first positive root of the equation

$$\operatorname{tg} \frac{z}{2} = (2\sigma^2 z)^{-1}. \quad (21)$$

The obtained z_0 value relates to the central wave number $k_0 = z_0\varepsilon^{-1}$ for excited modes of frequency $\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1}$,

$$\exp[i(k_0 + \theta_z + k)x + i\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1}t], \quad k = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots,$$

where we introduce the parameter $\theta_z = \theta_z(\varepsilon) \in [0, 1)$ which completes the critical value of $z_0\varepsilon^{-1}$ to an integer, and $\theta_z = 0$ if $z_0 = 0$, in order to provide periodic boundary conditions.

It is also convenient to introduce the parameter $\theta_\omega = \theta_\omega(\varepsilon) \in [0, 2\pi)$ which completes

the value of the expression $c\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1}$ to an integer multiple 2π . This expression relates to the main term of the series for the characteristic roots $\lambda_{kn} = i\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1}(1 + O(\varepsilon))$ under the critical conditions. Then we can omit the unbounded (under $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$) component in the expression $\exp(-ic\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1}(1 + O(\varepsilon))) = \exp(i\theta_\omega + O(1))$.

The following lemmas present the characteristic roots whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, in the small vicinity of the critical coupling,

$$d = d_0 + \varepsilon^2 d_1, \tag{22}$$

for models with bidirectional couplings given by the function $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$, unidirectional couplings given by $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$, and for oscillator models with weak dissipation $a^2 < 2$ or strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$.

Lemma 2.1. *Let $g(z) = g_1(z)$ is given by Eq.(16) and*

$$a^2 > 2. \tag{23}$$

Then $d_0\gamma_0 = p_0 = 1, \omega_0 = 0, z_0$ is given by Eq.(20) and for the roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ ($k, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$) of the equation (15), the real parts of which tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ the asymptotic equality

$$\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon) = \lambda_{0kn} + \varepsilon\lambda_{1kn} + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kn} + \dots, \tag{24}$$

is satisfied, where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{0kn} &= \pi ic^{-1} \left(2n + \frac{1}{2}\right), \\ \lambda_{1kn} &= -c^{-2} ia\pi \left(2n + \frac{1}{2}\right), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{2kn} &= c^{-3} \left(\pi \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2}\right)^{1/2} \left(2n + \frac{1}{2}\right) \right)^2 - ic^{-3} a^2 \pi \left(2n + \frac{1}{2}\right) + c^{-1} d_1 \gamma_0 p_0^{-1} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} c^{-1} \gamma_0''(z_0) (\theta_z + k)^2 (p_0 \gamma_0)^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.2. *Let $g(z) = g_1(z)$ is specified by Eq.(16) and*

$$0 < a^2 < 2. \tag{25}$$

Then $\omega_0 > 0, z_0$ is given by Eq.(20) and for the roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ ($k, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$) of the equation (15), whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, the asymptotic equality

$$\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon) = i\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \lambda_{0n} + \varepsilon\lambda_{1kn} + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kn} + \dots \tag{26}$$

is satisfied, where

$$\lambda_{0n} = ic^{-1} \left[\pi \left(2n + \frac{1}{2}\right) + \theta_\omega - \Omega_0 \right],$$

$$\lambda_{1kn} = ic^{-1} \varkappa^{-1} (2\omega_0 - ia) \lambda_{0n}, \quad \varkappa = p_0 \exp(i\Omega_0),$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{2kn} &= c^{-1} \left[\left(\varkappa^{-1} - \frac{1}{2} (-2\omega_0 + ia)^2 \varkappa^{-2} \right) \lambda_{0n}^2 + d_1 p_0^{-1} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_0''(z_0) (\theta_z + k)^2 (p_0 \gamma_0)^{-1} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - (c\varkappa)^{-1} 2i\omega_0 \varkappa^{-1} (2\omega_0 - ia) \lambda_{0n} - i\varkappa^{-1} a \lambda_{0n} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Now, we took into account that the expression

$$(-2\omega_0 + ia)P(\omega_0)^{-1} = P'(\omega_0)P(\omega_0)^{-1} = i\Omega'(\omega_0) = 2ia^{-1} \quad (27)$$

is purely imaginary that follows from the obvious relations $p'(\omega_0) = 0$, $P'(\omega) = (p'(\omega) + i\Omega'(\omega)p(\omega)) \exp(i\Omega(\omega))$ and $P'(\omega_0) = i\Omega'(\omega_0)p_0 \exp(i\Omega_0) = -2\omega_0 + ia$.

Then the conditions and

$$\Re \left(\varkappa^{-1} - \frac{1}{2}(-2\omega_0 + ia)^2 \varkappa^{-2} \right) < 0 \quad \Re \lambda_{1kn} = 0$$

are satisfied as follows from Eq.(27).

Lemma 2.3. *Let condition (17) be satisfied and let $a^2 > 2$. Then $d_0\gamma_0 = p_0 = 1, \omega_0 = 0, z_0$ is given by Eq.(21) and for the roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$, ($k, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$) of Eq.(15) whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ the asymptotic equality is satisfied,*

$$\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon) = \lambda_{0kn} + \varepsilon\lambda_{1kn} + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kn} + \dots, \quad (28)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{0kn} &= \left[i\pi \left(\frac{1}{2} + 2n \right) + \frac{i}{2}(z_0 + \varepsilon(\theta_z + k)) \right] c^{-1}, \\ \lambda_{1kn} &= -i\frac{a}{c^2} \left(\pi \left(\frac{1}{2} + 2n \right) + \frac{z_0}{2} \right) - \frac{1}{2c}(\theta_z + k), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{2kn} &= \left(\frac{2\pi n}{c} \right)^2 \left[\frac{2-a^2}{c} \right] + \frac{2\pi n}{c} \left[\frac{\pi}{2c^2}(2-a^2) + \frac{z_0}{c^2}(2-a^2) + i\frac{a^2}{c} \right] + d_0c^{-1}\gamma''(z_0)k^2 \\ &\quad + 2d_0c^{-1}\gamma''(z_0)\theta_z k + B_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_1 &= c^{-1}d_1\gamma_0 + c^{-1}d_0\gamma''(z_0)\theta_z^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{\pi^2}{2c^3} \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2} \right) (1 + z_0)^2 - \frac{ia^2}{2c^2}(\pi + z_0). \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.4. *Let the condition (17) be satisfied and let $0 < a^2 < 2$. Then $\omega_0 > 0, z_0$ is given by Eq.(21) and for the roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ ($k, n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$) of Eq.(15), whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, the asymptotic equality is satisfied,*

$$\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon) = i\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \lambda_{0n} + \varepsilon\lambda_{1kn} + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kn} + \dots, \quad (29)$$

where

$$\lambda_{0n} = ic^{-1} \left[\pi \left(2n + \frac{1}{2} \right) + \theta_\omega - \Omega_0 + \frac{z_0}{2} \right],$$

$$\lambda_{1kn} = \frac{i}{2}c^{-1}(\theta_z + k) - 2(ac)^{-1}\lambda_{0n}, \quad (30)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{2kn} &= -2c^{-3}a^{-2}\lambda_{0n}^2 + d_1(cd_0)^{-1} + d_0(c\gamma_0)^{-1}\gamma''(z_0)(\theta_z + k)^2 \\ &\quad - (c\varkappa)^{-1} \left[\lambda_{0n}^2 + (2i\omega_0 + a) \left(-\frac{2}{a}\lambda_{0n} + \frac{1}{2}(\theta_z + k) \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Summarizing, at the critical coupling level

there are infinitely roots with real parts closed

to zero, so critical cases under consideration have (asymptotically) infinite dimension.

2.1. Solutions to the linearized problem

Having the characteristic roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ determined, it is possible to write down the partial solution to the linear boundary value problem (13), (14) as

$$u_{kn}(t, x, \varepsilon) = \exp(i(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z + k)x + \lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)t).$$

Then the general solution to Eqs.(13), (14) reads as

$$u(t, x, \varepsilon) = \sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\xi_{kn} u_{kn}(t, x, \varepsilon) + \bar{\xi}_{kn} \bar{u}_{kn}(t, x, \varepsilon) \right), \quad (31)$$

where ξ_{kn} — arbitrary complex constants.

Remark. Together with the roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ there are roots $\bar{\lambda}_{kn}(\varepsilon)$, which correspond to the counter propagated waves

$$\bar{u}_{kn}(t, x, \varepsilon) = \exp(-i(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z + k)x + \bar{\lambda}_{kn}(\varepsilon)t).$$

Since the dependence on z in the right-hand side of the characteristic equation (15) is even, then the wave numbers $\pm(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z + k)$ correspond to the same root $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$. Under the conditions of lemma 2.1 the equality $\tilde{u}_{kn}(t, x, \varepsilon) = \bar{u}_{kn}(t, x, \varepsilon)$ is satisfied, but under the conditions of lemma 2.2 this is no longer the case.

3. Nonlinear analysis of model with bidirectional couplings

Here we look for solutions to the nonlinear problem (11),(12) with $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$ and consider separately oscillators with strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$ and oscillators with weak dissipation $a^2 < 2$.

3.1. Oscillators with strong dissipation

If $a^2 > 2$ the critical coupling level corresponding to instability of zero equilibrium is

defined as

$$d_0 = |\gamma_0|^{-1} \quad (32)$$

and the equalities $\omega_0 = 0, \Omega_0 = 0, p_0 = 1$ are valid. Using Eq.(31) and the characteristic roots given by Lemma 2.1 we write the general solution to the linearized problem as

$$u(t, x, \varepsilon) = E(t, x) \sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kn} \exp \left(ikx + 2i\pi n c^{-1}(1 - \varepsilon c^{-1}a)t + (\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau \right) = E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1), \quad (33)$$

where $E(t, x) = \exp(i(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z)x + i\pi(2c)^{-1}(1 - \varepsilon ac^{-1})t)$ is the carrier wave, $\xi_{kn}(\tau) = \xi_{kn} \exp((\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau)$ are coefficients of the expansion of $\xi(\tau, x, x_1)$ into Fourier series by 2π -periodic argument x and c -periodic argument $x_1 = (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1}a)t$, $\tau = \varepsilon^2 t$ is «slow» time variable.

Solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) can be found as series by degrees of ε ,

$$u = \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1) + \bar{c}\bar{c}) + \varepsilon^3 U_3(t, \tau, x, x_1) + \dots, \quad (34)$$

where we denote by $\bar{c}\bar{c}$ the summand complexly conjugate to the previous one. Let us substitute Eq.(34) into Eq.(11) and collect the coefficients at the same degrees of ε . Then at the first degree of ε we obtain the correct equality. Equating the coefficients at ε^3 , we arrive at the equation for the complex function $\xi(\tau, x, x_1)$,

$$c \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} = \left(\frac{a^2}{2} - 1 \right) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + (2\gamma_0)^{-1} \gamma''(z_0) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} - i\gamma_0^{-1} \gamma''(z_0) \theta_z \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} + ic^{-1} \left(a^2 - \frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2} \right) \right) \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} + B_0 \xi + 3b_1 \xi |\xi|^2, \quad (35)$$

with boundary conditions

$$\xi(\tau, x, x_1 + c) \equiv \xi(\tau, x, x_1) \equiv \xi(\tau, x + 2\pi, x_1), \quad (36)$$

where

$$B_0 = c^{-2} \pi^2 \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2} \right) + ia^{2-2} \frac{1}{2} \pi + \frac{1}{2} \gamma''(z_0) \theta_z^2 + 2d_1 c^{-1} \gamma_0.$$

Note, when deriving Eq.(35) the relations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\xi}{dt} &= \varepsilon^2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} (1 - \varepsilon a c^{-1}), \\ \xi_{t-c} &= \xi(\tau - \varepsilon^2 c, x, x_1 - c(1 - \varepsilon a c^{-1})) \\ &= \xi(\tau, x, x_1) - \varepsilon^2 c \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} + \varepsilon a \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon^2 a^2 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + o(\varepsilon^2), \end{aligned}$$

were taken into account.

Let fix arbitrarily the value $\theta_{0z} \in [0, 1)$ and denote by $\varepsilon_n = \varepsilon_n(\theta_{0z})$ such a sequence that $\varepsilon_n \rightarrow 0$ at $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $\theta_z(\varepsilon_n, \theta_{0z}) = \theta_{0z}$. The above constructions justify the following result.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $a^2 > 2$ and conditions (22), (32) are satisfied. Let $\theta_{0z} \in [0, 1)$ be arbitrarily fixed and the boundary value problem (35), (36) at $\theta_z = \theta_{0z}$ has bounded at $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, $x \in [0, 2\pi]$, $x_1 \in [0, c]$, solution of $\xi(\tau, x, x_1)$. Then the function $u(t, x, \varepsilon) = \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1) + \overline{cc}) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(\tau, x, x_1)$ satisfies the boundary value problem (11), (12) with accuracy to $o(\varepsilon^3)$.*

Thus the parabolic boundary value problem (35), (36) is a quasinormal form for the boundary value problem (11), (12).

3.2. Oscillators with weak dissipation

If $a^2 < 2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_0 &= \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2} \right)^{1/2}, \quad p_0 = \frac{a^2}{2} (4 - a^2)^{1/2}, \\ d_0 &= p_0 |\gamma_0|^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

in the critical case. To each root $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ given by Lemma 2.2 there corresponds the Euler partial

solution of the linear boundary value problem (13), (14)

$$u_{kn}^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) = \exp(\pm i(z_0 \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z + k)x + \lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)t),$$

which is convenient to rewrite as

$$\begin{aligned} u_{kn}^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) \\ = E^\pm(t, x) \exp(ikx + 2i\pi n x_1 + (\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} E^\pm(t, x) &= \exp \left(ic^{-1}(\omega_0 \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_\omega - \Omega_0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \varepsilon ic^{-1} \varkappa^{-1}(2\omega_0 - ia) \cdot (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0))t \right. \\ &\quad \left. \pm i(z_0 \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z)x \right). \end{aligned}$$

Then the general solution reads as

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kn}^\pm u_{kn}^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) \\ &= E^\pm(t, x) \sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kn}^\pm(\tau) \exp(ikx + 2i\pi n x_1) \\ &= E^\pm(t, x) \xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1). \end{aligned}$$

where $\tau = \varepsilon^2 t$, $x_1 = (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1} R)t$, $R = \varkappa^{-1}(2\omega_0 - ia) \cdot ic^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0)$ and $\Im R = 0$, ξ_{kn}^\pm are arbitrary complex constants, and $\xi_{kn}^\pm(\tau) = \xi_{kn}^\pm \exp((\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau)$. Functions $\xi_{kn}^\pm(\tau)$ are the Fourier coefficients of the 2π -periodic by x and c -periodic by x_1 functions $\xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1)$.

Solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) can be found as

$$u(t, x) = u^+(t, x) + u^-(t, x), \quad (38)$$

$$\begin{aligned} u^\pm(t, x) &= \varepsilon(\xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1)E^\pm(t, x) + \overline{cc}) \\ &\quad + \varepsilon^3 u_3(t, \tau, x, x_1) + \dots, \end{aligned}$$

all terms in the series depend periodically on t , x and x_1 .

Let us substitute (38) into (11) and equate the coefficients at the same powers of ε . At the first step we obtain the correct equality, and, collecting the coefficients at ε^3 , we obtain the

equation with respect to u_3 . From the condition of its solvability in the specified class of functions we arrive at the equation

$$c \frac{\partial \xi^\pm}{\partial \tau} = A_1 \frac{\partial^2 \xi^\pm}{\partial x_1^2} + A_2 \frac{\partial \xi^\pm}{\partial x_1} + A_3 \xi^\pm + B_1 \frac{\partial^2 \xi^\pm}{\partial x^2} + B_2 \frac{\partial \xi^\pm}{\partial x} + \beta \xi^\pm (|\xi^\pm|^2 + 2|\xi^\mp|^2), \tag{39}$$

with periodic boundary conditions

$$\xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1 + c) \equiv \xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1) \equiv \xi^\pm(\tau, x + 2\pi, x_1), \tag{40}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= -c^{-2} \left[\varkappa^{-1} - \frac{1}{2} (ia - 2\omega_0)^2 \varkappa^{-2} \right], \\ A_2 &= c^{-2} \left[-2(\varkappa^{-1} - \frac{1}{2} (ia - 2\omega_0)^2 \varkappa^{-2} (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0)) + c\varkappa^{-2} 2\omega_0(2\omega_0 - ia) + c^2 \varkappa^{-1} a(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) \right], \\ A_3 &= c^{-2} \left[\frac{1}{2} (ia - 2\omega_0) \varkappa^2 (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0)^2 - \varkappa^{-1} \right] + d_1 c^{-1} p_0^{-1} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma''(z_0) c^{-1} \theta_z^2 (p_0 \gamma_0)^{-1} - i(c\varkappa)^{-2} 2i\omega_0(2\omega_0 - ia) \times (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) - i(c\varkappa)^{-1} a(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0), \\ B_1 &= \frac{1}{2} \gamma''(z_0) (p_0 \gamma_0)^{-1}, \\ B_2 &= \gamma''(z_0) \theta_z (p_0 \gamma_0)^{-1}, \\ \beta &= b_1 + i\omega_0 b_2 - \omega_0^2 b_3 - i\omega_0^3 b_4. \end{aligned}$$

In order to formulate the final result we fix arbitrarily $\theta_{0\omega} \in [0, 2\pi)$ and consider the sequence $\varepsilon_s = \varepsilon_s(\theta_{0\omega})$, $s = 1, 2, \dots$, defined by the condition $\theta_\omega(\varepsilon_s(\theta_{0\omega})) = \theta_{0\omega}$. Let us denote by $\Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$ all limit points of the sequence $\theta_z(\varepsilon_s(\theta_{0\omega}))$ from the interval $[0, 1]$ and by θ_{0z} the limit element of $\Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$ and let the subsequence $\varepsilon_{s\Gamma}$ of the sequence ε_s be such that

$$\lim_{\Gamma \rightarrow \infty} \theta_z(\varepsilon_{s\Gamma}) = \theta_{0z}.$$

It is possible that the set $\Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$ coincides with the segment $[0, 1]$ or this set consists of a single element.

Theorem 3.2. *Let $0 < a^2 < 2$ and $d_0 = p_0 |\gamma_0|^{-1}$. Fix arbitrarily $\theta_{0\omega} \in [0, 2\pi)$ and let $\theta_{0z} \in \Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$. Let $\xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1)$ — bounded at $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, $x \in [0, 2\pi]$, $x_1 \in [0, c]$, the solution of the boundary value problem (39), (40). Then the function*

$$u(t, x, \varepsilon) = \varepsilon (\xi^+(\tau, x, x_1) E^+(t, x) + \bar{c}c + \xi^-(\tau, x, x_1) E^-(t, x) + \bar{c}c) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(t, \tau, x, x_1)$$

at $\tau = \varepsilon^2 t$, $x_1 = (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1} R)t$ on the sequence $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{s\Gamma}$ satisfies the boundary value problem (11), (12) with accuracy to $o(\varepsilon_{s\Gamma}^3)$.

Thus, the boundary value problem (39), (40) is a quasinormal form for the original boundary value problem (11), (12). In this critical case we expect rapid oscillations in the system (11), (12), since the main terms of the characteristic roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ are close to $i\omega_0 \varepsilon^{-1}$.

4. Nonlinear analysis of model with bidirectional couplings

Here we look for solutions to the nonlinear problem (11), (12) with $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$ and consider separately oscillators with strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$ and oscillators with weak dissipation $a^2 < 2$.

4.1. Oscillators with strong dissipation.

If $a^2 > 2$ the critical conditions is determined by the equality

$$d_0 = |\gamma_0|^{-1}, \omega_0 = 0, \Omega_0 = 0, p_0 = 1. \tag{41}$$

Using Eq.(31) and the characteristic roots given by Lemma 2.3, the solution to the linearized system can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x, \varepsilon) &= E(t, x) \sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kn} \exp \left(ikx + 2i\pi n c^{-1} (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1} a)t + (\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau \right) \\ &= E(t, x) \xi(\tau, x, x_1), \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

where $\tau = \varepsilon^2 t$ is «slow» time variable,

$$E(t, x) = \exp\left(i\left(\frac{1}{2}(z_0 + \pi + \varepsilon\theta_z)\right) + i(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z)x + i\pi(2c)^{-1}(1 - \varepsilon ac^{-1})t\right),$$

$\xi_{kn}(\tau) = \xi_{kn} \exp((\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau)$ are coefficients of the expansion $\xi(\tau, x, x_1)$ into Fourier series by 2π -periodic argument x and c -periodic argument $x_1 = (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1}a)t$.

Solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) can be found as the series of ε degrees,

$$u = \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1) + \overline{c\bar{c}}) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(\tau, x, x_1) + \dots \quad (43)$$

Let us substitute (43) into (11) and collect the coefficients at the same degrees of ε . Then at the first degree of ε we obtain the correct equality. Equating the coefficients at ε^3 , we arrive at the equation for the unknown complex function $\xi(\tau, x, x_1)$,

$$\begin{aligned} c \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} &= \left(\frac{1}{2}a^2 - 1\right) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + (2\gamma_0)^{-1} \gamma''(z_0) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} \\ &\quad - i\gamma_0^{-1} \gamma''(z_0) \theta_z \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} \\ &\quad + ic^{-1} \left(a^2 - \frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2\right)\right) \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} \\ &\quad + B_0 \xi + 3b_1 \xi |\xi|^2, \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

with periodic boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(\tau, x, x_1 + c) &\equiv \xi(\tau, x, x_1) \\ &\equiv \xi(\tau, x + 2\pi, x_1), \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} B_0 &= c^{-2} \pi^2 \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2\right) + ia^2 c^{-2} \frac{1}{2} \pi \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \gamma''(z_0) \theta_z^2 + 2d_1 c^{-1} \gamma_0 \end{aligned}$$

Let us fix arbitrarily the value $\theta_{0z} \in [0, 1)$ and denote by $\varepsilon_n = \varepsilon_n(\theta_{0z})$ such a sequence that $\varepsilon_n \rightarrow 0$ at $n \rightarrow \infty$ and $\theta_z(\varepsilon_n, \theta_{0z}) = \theta_{0z}$. The following theorem summarizes the results obtained above.

Theorem 4.1. *Let $a^2 > 2$ and conditions (22), (41) are satisfied. Let $\theta_{0z} \in [0, 1)$ be arbitrarily fixed and the boundary value problem (44), (45) at $\theta_z = \theta_{0z}$ has the solution $\xi(\tau, x, x_1)$ bounded at $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, $x \in [0, 2\pi]$, $x_1 \in [0, c]$. Then the function $u(t, x, \varepsilon) = \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1) + \overline{c\bar{c}}) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(\tau, x, x_1)$ satisfies the boundary value problem (11), (12) with accuracy to $o(\varepsilon^3)$.*

Thus the parabolic boundary value problem (44), (45) is a quasinormal form which describes the local dynamics of the original problem (11), (12).

4.2. Oscillators with weak dissipation.

If $a^2 < 2$ is valid, the main terms of the characteristic roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ are $i\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1}$, i. e., the roots are asymptotically large. Therefore, we expect rapid oscillations in the boundary value problem (11), (12). Remind that in this case

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_0 &= \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{2}\right)^{1/2}, \quad p_0 = \frac{a^2}{2}(4 - a^2)^{1/2}, \\ d_0 &= p_0 |\gamma_0|^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

The Euler solutions of the linear boundary value problem (13), (14) corresponding to the characteristic roots $\lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)$ given by Lemma 2.4 read as

$$u_{kn}^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) = \exp\left(\pm i(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z + k)x + \lambda_{kn}(\varepsilon)t\right).$$

It is convenient to rewrite these functions as

$$\begin{aligned} u_{kn}^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) &= E^\pm(t, x) \exp\left(ikx + 2i\pi n x_1 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau\right), \end{aligned}$$

where the carrier counter propagated waves are

$$\begin{aligned} E^\pm(t, x) &= \exp\left(i(c^{-1}\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1} + c^{-1}\left(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0 + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \varepsilon c^{-1} \varkappa^{-1}(2\omega_0 - ia) \cdot ic^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0))t \right. \\ &\quad \left. \pm i(z_0\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z)x\right), \end{aligned}$$

$\tau = \varepsilon^2 t$ is slow time variable, $x_1 = (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1} R)t$, where

$$R = \varkappa^{-1}(2\omega_0 - ia) \cdot ic^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) = 2a^{-1}, \quad \Im R = 0.$$

The general solution can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kn}^{\pm} u_{kn}^{\pm}(t, x, \varepsilon) \\ &= E^{\pm}(t, x) \sum_{k,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kn}^{\pm}(\tau) \exp(ikx + 2i\pi n x_1) \\ &= E^{\pm}(t, x) \xi^{\pm}(\tau, x, x_1), \end{aligned}$$

where $\xi_{kn}^{\pm}(\tau) = \xi_{kn}^{\pm} \exp((\lambda_{2kn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau)$ are the Fourier coefficients of function $\xi^{\pm}(\tau, x, x_1)$ and they are 2π -periodic by variable x and c -periodic by variable x_1 .

Solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) can be found as the sum of series,

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x) &= u^+(t, x) + u^-(t, x), \quad (47) \\ u^{\pm}(t, x) &= \varepsilon(\xi^{\pm}(\tau, x, x_1)E^{\pm}(t, x) + \overline{c\bar{c}}) \\ &\quad + \varepsilon^3 u_3(t, \tau, x, x_1) + \dots, \end{aligned}$$

where all functions depend periodically on t, x and x_1 .

Let us substitute the series (47) into Eq.(11) and equate the coefficients at the same powers of ε . At the first step we obtain the correct equality, and by collecting the coefficients at ε^3 we obtain the equation with respect to u_3 . From the condition of its solvability in the specified class of functions we arrive at the equation

$$\begin{aligned} c \frac{\partial \xi^{\pm}}{\partial \tau} &= A_1 \frac{\partial^2 \xi^{\pm}}{\partial x_1^2} + A_2 \frac{\partial \xi^{\pm}}{\partial x_1} + A_3 \frac{\partial^2 \xi^{\pm}}{\partial x^2} + A_4 \frac{\partial \xi^{\pm}}{\partial x} \\ &\quad + A_5 \xi + \beta \xi^{\pm} (|\xi^{\pm}|^2 + 2|\xi^{\mp}|^2), \quad (48) \end{aligned}$$

with periodic boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(\tau, x, x_1 + c) &\equiv \xi(\tau, x, x_1) \\ &\equiv \xi(\tau, x + 2\pi, x_1), \quad (49) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= 2a^2 - (p_0 \exp(i\Omega_0))^{-1}, \quad \Re A_1 > 0, \\ A_2 &= 2iA_1 l c^{-1} + 4a^{-2}, \\ A_3 &= d_0 \gamma_0^{-1} \gamma''(z_0), \\ A_4 &= -2i\theta_z d_0 \gamma_0^{-1} \gamma''(z_0) - 2(a^2 c)^{-1}, \\ A_5 &= A_1 l^2 + d_1 d_0^{-1} + d_0 \gamma_0^{-1} \gamma''(z_0) \theta_z^2 \\ &\quad - 4i(a^2 c)^{-1} l + a^{-1} \theta_z, \\ l &= \theta_\omega - \Omega_0 + \frac{1}{2}(\pi + z_0), \\ \beta &= b_1 + i\omega_0 b_2 - \omega_0^2 b_3 - i\omega_0^3 b_4. \end{aligned}$$

In order to formulate the final result, we fix arbitrarily $\theta_{0\omega} \in [0, 2\pi)$. Let the sequence $\varepsilon_s = \varepsilon_s(\theta_{0\omega})$ be defined from the condition $\theta_\omega(\varepsilon_s(\theta_{0\omega})) = \theta_{0\omega} (s = 1, 2, \dots)$. Denote also all limit points of the sequence $\theta_z(\varepsilon_s(\theta_{0\omega}))$ from the interval $[0, 1]$ by $\Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$ and the limit element of $\Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$ by θ_{0z} . Let the subsequence ε_{s_Γ} of the sequence ε_s be such that

$$\lim_{\Gamma \rightarrow \infty} \theta_z(\varepsilon_{s_\Gamma}) = \theta_{0z}.$$

The following theorem summarizes the above results.

Theorem 4.2. *Let $0 < a^2 < 2$ and $d_0 = p_0 |\gamma_0|^{-1}$. Fix arbitrarily $\theta_{0\omega} \in [0, 2\pi)$ and let $\theta_{0z} \in \Gamma(\theta_{0\omega})$. Let $\xi^{\pm}(\tau, x, x_1)$ is the solution of the boundary value problem (39), (40) bounded at $\tau \rightarrow \infty, x \in [0, 2\pi], x_1 \in [0, c]$. Then the function*

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x, \varepsilon) &= \varepsilon(\xi^+(\tau, x, x_1)E^+(t, x) + \overline{c\bar{c}} \\ &\quad + \xi^-(\tau, x, x_1)E^-(t, x) + \overline{c\bar{c}}) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(t, \tau, x, x_1) \end{aligned}$$

at $\tau = \varepsilon^2 t, x_1 = (1 - \varepsilon c^{-1} R)t$ on the sequence $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_{s_\Gamma}$ satisfies the boundary value problem (11), (12) with accuracy to $o(\varepsilon_{s_\Gamma}^3)$.

Thus, the boundary value problem (39), (40) is a quasinormal form which determined the local dynamics of the original boundary value problem (11), (12).

5. Quasinormal forms for models with small σ

In the original boundary value problem, the coupling function $\Phi(s)$ specified by Eqs.(8), (9) depends on the parameter σ . Here we assume that σ is small,

$$\sigma = \varepsilon\sigma_1, \quad \sigma_1 > 0. \tag{50}$$

This means that only those elements of the ring that are located near the points $x \pm \varepsilon$ directly affect each specific element at point x , i.e. the distributed model is most adequate to the discrete model of a chain.

5.1. Model with bidirectional couplings

First we consider the coupling function $\Phi(s) = \Phi_1(s)$ and oscillators with strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$. Under the condition (50) and $\varepsilon \ll 1$ we have

$$\gamma(z) = \gamma_0(z) \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}\varepsilon^2\sigma_1^2 z^2 + O(\varepsilon^4) \right),$$

where $\gamma_0(z) = 2i \sin z$. The maximal value of $|\gamma_0(z)| = 2$ is achieved at $z = z_m^\pm$,

$$z_m^\pm = \pi \left(2m \pm \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots,$$

at the critical conditions $d_0 = 1/2$, $\omega_0 = \Omega_0 = 0$, $p_0 = 1$. The modes with wave numbers

$$\pi(2m \pm 1/2)\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_{zm} + k, \quad k, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots,$$

where

$$\theta_{zm} = \begin{cases} 0, & N=4P \\ 3/4, & N=4P+1 \\ 1/2, & N=4P+2 \\ 1/4, & N=4P+3 \end{cases}$$

are excited at the same critical conditions. Note, we have introduced the correction θ_{zm} to make wave numbers be integer in order to provide the periodic boundary condition.

By $u_{kmn}(t, x)$ we denote the Euler solutions of the linear problem (13), (14)

$$u_{kmn}^\pm(t, x) = \exp \left[i \left(\pi \left(2m + \frac{1}{2} \right) \varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_{zm} + k \right) x + \lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon) t \right].$$

Substituting these expressions into the linear problem (13), (14) at $d = d_0 + \varepsilon^2 d_1$, we find those characteristic roots $\lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon)$ whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

Lemma 5.1. *Let the conditions (22), (23), (50) be satisfied. Then the asymptotic representation of the characteristic roots*

$$\lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon) = c^{-1} i \pi \left(2n \pm \frac{1}{2} \right) + \varepsilon \lambda_{1kmn}^\pm + \varepsilon^2 \lambda_{2kmn}^\pm + \dots,$$

is valid, where

$$\lambda_{1kmn}^\pm = iac^{-2} \pi \left(2n \pm \frac{1}{2} \right),$$

$$\begin{aligned} c\lambda_{2kmn}^\pm &= \frac{1}{2}(2 - a^2)c^{-2}\pi^2 \left(2n \pm \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \\ &\quad - ia^2c^{-2}\pi \left(2n \pm \frac{1}{2} \right) + 4d_1 - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2\pi^2 \left(2m \pm \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4}(k \pm \theta_{zm})^2. \end{aligned}$$

Then the general solution of the linear boundary value problem reads as

$$\begin{aligned} u^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) &= \\ &= \sum_{k,m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kmn}^\pm \exp \left[i \left(\pi \left(2m \pm \frac{1}{2} \right) \varepsilon^{-1} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \pm \theta_{zm} + k \right) x + \lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon) t \right]. \end{aligned}$$

It can be written in the form

$$u^\pm(t, x, \varepsilon) = E^\pm(t, x) \xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1, y), \tag{51}$$

where

$$E^\pm(t, x) = \exp \left[\pm i \frac{\pi}{2} \left(c^{-1}(1 - \varepsilon ac^{-1})t + (\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_{zm})x \right) \right],$$

$$\xi^\pm(\tau, x, x_1, y)$$

$$= \sum_{k,m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kmn}^\pm(\tau) \exp \left[ikx + 2i\pi nc^{-1}x_1 + 2i\pi my \right],$$

$$\xi_{kmn}^\pm(\tau) = \xi_{kmn}^\pm \exp(\lambda_{2kmn}^\pm + O(\varepsilon)\tau),$$

$$y = x\varepsilon^{-1}, \quad x_1 = (1 + \varepsilon ac^{-1})t.$$

Since $E^-(t, x) = \overline{E^+}(t, x)$, we look for solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) as series on ε degrees,

$$u(t, x) = \varepsilon \left(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1, y) + \overline{c\bar{c}} \right) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(\tau, x, x_1, y) + \dots \quad (52)$$

Substituting (52) into (11) and performing the standard steps, we arrive at the boundary value problem for determining the unknown function $\xi(\tau, x, y, x_1)$,

$$c \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} = - \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2 \right) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{a^2}{c} - \frac{i\pi}{c} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2 \right) \right) + \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} + i\theta_z \cdot \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} - \frac{\sigma_1^2}{2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} + i\sigma_1^2 \pi^2 \cdot \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial y} + \left(2d_1 + \frac{\pi^2}{4c^2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2 \right) + i \frac{a^2 \pi^2}{c^2} - \frac{1}{2}\theta_z^2 - \frac{1}{8}\sigma_1^2 \pi^2 \right) \xi + b_1 \xi |\xi|^2, \quad (53)$$

$$\xi(\tau, x + 2\pi, x_1, y) \equiv \xi(\tau, x, x_1, y) \equiv \xi(\tau, x, x_1 + c, y) \equiv \xi(\tau, x, x_1, y + 1). \quad (54)$$

The following theorem summarizes the above result.

Theorem 5.1. *Let conditions (22), (23), (50) be satisfied. Let $\theta_{z0} \in [0, 1)$ is arbitrarily fixed, and let $\xi(\tau, x, x_1, y)$ is the solution of the boundary value problem (53)–(54) which is bounded at $\tau \rightarrow$*

$\infty, x \in [0, 2\pi], y \in [0, 1], x_1 \in [0, c]$. Then the function

$$u(t, x) = \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x, x_1, y) + \overline{c\bar{c}}) + \varepsilon^3 u_3(\tau, x, x_1, y)$$

satisfies the boundary value problem (11), (12) with accuracy $o(\varepsilon_s^3)$ at $\theta_z = \theta_{z0}$ and on the sequence $\varepsilon_s(\theta_z(\varepsilon_s(\theta_{z0}) = \theta_{z0})$.

5.2. Model with unidirectional couplings

Here we look for the solutions to Eqs.(11), (12) with the coupling function $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$, for which $\sigma = \varepsilon\sigma_1$, and consider oscillators with strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$.

The critical conditions $d_0 = 1/2, \omega_0 = \Omega_0 = 0, p_0 = 1$ are realized when $\gamma_0(z_m) = -2$ at

$$z = z_{mk} = \pi(2m + 1) + k; \quad k, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$$

Note, the set of modes with wave numbers

$$\pi(2m + 1)\varepsilon^{-1} + \theta_z + k, \quad k, m = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots,$$

where

$$\theta_z = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } N - \text{even,} \\ \frac{1}{2}, & \text{if } N - \text{odd} \end{cases}$$

can be excited at the same critical conditions. We have introduced the correction θ_z taking into account $\varepsilon = 2\pi N^{-1}$ in order to make wave numbers integer and, in this way, to provide the periodic boundary condition.

Let the number of oscillators N is even and $\theta_z = 0$.

Substituting expressions for modes into the linearized equation (13) at $d = d_0 + \varepsilon^2 d_1$, we find those characteristic roots $\lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon)$ whose real

parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$,

$$\lambda_{kmn}(\varepsilon) = i\pi(2n + 1) + \varepsilon\lambda_{1kmn} + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kmn} + \dots, \tag{55}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{1kmn} &= -iac^{-2}\pi(2n + 1) + \frac{1}{2}ic^{-1}k, \\ c\lambda_{2kmn} &= \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2\right)(\pi(2n + 1)c^{-1})^2 - \frac{1}{8}k^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2(\pi(2m + 1))^2 - \frac{1}{2}a\pi(2n + 1)k \\ &\quad + ia^2c^{-1}\pi(2n + 1) - ia(2c)^{-1}k + 2d_1. \end{aligned}$$

Then solutions of the linear boundary value problem (13), (14) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x) &= \sum_{k,m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kmn} \exp [i\pi(2m + 1)\varepsilon^{-1}x \\ &\quad + kx + (i\pi(2n + 1)(1 - \varepsilon ac^{-1}) \\ &\quad - \varepsilon a(2c)^{-1}k)t + (\lambda_{2kmn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau] \\ &= \sum_{k,m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kmn}(\tau) \exp [i\pi(2m + 1)y \\ &\quad + i\pi(2n + 1)x_1 + ikx_2] \\ &= \xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y), \end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_{kmn}(\tau) &= \xi_{kmn} \cdot \exp[(\lambda_{2kmn} + O(\varepsilon))\tau], \\ x_1 &= (1 - \varepsilon ac^{-1})t, \quad x_2 = x - \varepsilon a(2c)^{-1}t, \\ y &= x\varepsilon^{-1}. \end{aligned} \tag{57}$$

Using the representation (56), we seek solutions to the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) as the series of ε degrees,

$$u(t, x, \varepsilon) = \varepsilon\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y) + \varepsilon u_3(\tau, x_1, x_2, y) + \dots$$

Substituting this series into Eq.(11) and performing the standard calculations, we get the parabolic boundary value problem

$$\begin{aligned} c\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} &= \left(\frac{1}{2}a^2 - 1\right)\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{1}{8}\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + ac^{-1}\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} \\ &\quad - a(2c)^{-1}\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_2} + 2d_1\xi + b_1\xi|\xi|^2, \end{aligned} \tag{58}$$

with boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} -\xi(\tau, x_1 + c, x_2, y) &\equiv \xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y) \\ &\equiv \xi(\tau, x_1, x_2 + 2\pi, y), \end{aligned} \tag{59}$$

$$-\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y + 1) \equiv \xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y), \tag{60}$$

from which one can find the real function $\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y)$. This boundary value problem is a quasinormal form in the considered case.

Let the number of oscillators N is odd and $\theta_z = 1/2$.

Substituting expressions for modes into the linear problem (13), (14) at $d = d_0 + \varepsilon^2 d_1$, we find those characteristic roots $\lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon)$ whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{kmn}(\varepsilon) &= i\pi(2n + 1) + \varepsilon\lambda_{1kmn} \\ &\quad + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kmn} + \dots, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{1kmn} &= -iac^{-2}\pi(2n + 1) + \frac{1}{2}ic^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{2} + k\right), \\ c\lambda_{2kmn} &= \left(1 - \frac{1}{2}a^2\right)(\pi(2n + 1)c^{-1})^2 - \frac{1}{8}k^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2(\pi(2m + 1))^2 - \frac{1}{2}a\pi(2n + 1)c^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{2} + k\right) \\ &\quad + ia^2c^{-2}\pi(2n + 1) - ia(2c)^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{2} + k\right) + 2d_1. \end{aligned}$$

The excited modes in the linear boundary value problem (13), (14) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x) &= E(t, x) \sum_{k,m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kmn} \exp [i\pi(2m + 1)y \\ &\quad + i\pi(2n + 1)x_1 + ikx_2] = E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$E(t, x) = \exp \left[i\frac{1}{2}(x + \varepsilon(2c)^{-1}t) \right] = \exp \left[i\frac{1}{2}x_2 \right].$$

Solutions to the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) can be sought as a series in ε powers,

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x, \varepsilon) &= \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y) + \bar{c}\bar{c}) \\ &\quad + \varepsilon^3 u_3(t, \tau, x_1, x_2, y) + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Let us substitute this series into (11). As a result of standard procedure, we obtain a parabolic boundary value problem for finding the complex function $\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y)$:

$$\begin{aligned} c \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} &= \left(\frac{1}{2}a^2 - 1\right) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{1}{8} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} \\ &- \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + \left(i \frac{a}{2} + ac^{-1}\right) \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} \\ &+ \left(\frac{i}{8} - a(2c)^{-1}\right) \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_2} + \left(2d_1 - \frac{1}{32} - \frac{ia}{4c}\right) \xi \\ &+ 3b_1 \xi |\xi|^2 \end{aligned} \tag{61}$$

with boundary conditions (59) and (60).

Remark. In the right part of Eq.(61) there is no summand of the form $\text{const} \cdot E^2(t, x) \xi^3$. This is due to the fact that $E(t, x) = \exp [i(x + (2c\varepsilon)^{-1}\tau)/2]$. As a result of the principle of averaging over a rapidly oscillating periodic argument τ (see, e.g., [27, 28]), the corresponding summand in the principal is nullified.

Eqs.(61),(59),(60) play the role of the quasinormal form which determines the local dynamics of the original system.

5.3. Model with unidirectional couplings and weak dissipation

Here we look for solutions of Eqs.(11),(12) with the function $\Phi(s) = \Phi_2(s)$, for which $\sigma = \varepsilon\sigma_1$, at $0 < a^2 < 2$. Then the critical conditions are determined by Eqs.(46).

First, we present those characteristic roots $\lambda_{kmn}^\pm(\varepsilon)$ whose real parts tend to zero at $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{kmn}(\varepsilon) &= i(\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1} + (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0)c^{-1}) + i\pi(2n + 1) \\ &+ \varepsilon\lambda_{1kmn} + \varepsilon^2\lambda_{2kmn} + \dots, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_{1kmn} &= -2i(ac)^{-1}R + i(2c)^{-1}(\theta_z + k), \\ R &= (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0 + \pi(2n + 1))c^{-1}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} c\lambda_{2kmn} &= -\frac{1}{2}(2a^{-1}R + \frac{1}{2}(\theta_z + k))^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2}(2a^{-1}R - \frac{1}{2}(\theta_z + k))(\theta_z + k) \\ &- c^{-1}(\theta_z + k)^2 + (p_0 \exp(i\Omega_0))^{-1}R^2 \\ &+ 2\omega_0(2a^{-1}R - \frac{1}{2}(\theta_z + k)) - 2ic^{-1}R \\ &+ ia(2c)^{-1}(\theta_z + k) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2(\pi(2m + 1))^2 + 2d_1p_0^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

The general solution of the linear boundary value problem (13), (14) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x) &= E(t, x) \sum_{k,m,n=-\infty}^{\infty} \xi_{kmn} \exp [i\pi(2n + 1)x_1 \\ &+ ikx_2 + i\pi(2m + 1)y] = E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} E(t, x) &= \exp [i(\omega_0\varepsilon^{-1} + (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0)c^{-1} \\ &\cdot (1 - 2\varepsilon ac^{-1}) + \varepsilon c^{-1}\theta_z)t + i\theta_z x], \end{aligned}$$

and the equalities (57) are valid for $x_{1,2}$ and y .

The solutions of the nonlinear boundary value problem (11), (12) can be found as a series in ε powers,

$$\begin{aligned} u(t, x, \varepsilon) &= \varepsilon(E(t, x)\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y) + \bar{c}\bar{c}) \\ &+ \varepsilon^3 u_3(t, \tau, x_1, x_2, y) + \dots, \end{aligned} \tag{62}$$

in which all functions are periodic on variables t, x_1, x_2 and y . Let us substitute the series (62) into Eq.(11) and equate the coefficients at the same powers of ε and at the same harmonics. As a result, we arrive at an equation with respect to u_3 , from the solvability condition of which in the specified class of functions we obtain the following boundary value problem for determining the unknown amplitude $\xi(\tau, x_1, x_2, y)$,

$$\begin{aligned} c \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \tau} &= H_1 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1^2} + H_2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_1} - \frac{1}{8} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_2^2} + H_3 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_2} \\ &+ \left(\frac{1}{4} - a^{-1}\right) \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma_1^2 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} \\ &+ H_4 \xi + 3\beta \xi |\xi|^2 \end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

with boundary conditions (59), (60), where

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1 &= -\varkappa^{-1} + \frac{1}{2}(ia - 2\omega_0)^2 \varkappa^{-2}, \\
 H_2 &= c^{-1} \left[-2(\varkappa^{-1} - \frac{1}{2}(ia - 2\omega_0)^2 \varkappa^{-2}) \right. \\
 &\quad \cdot (\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) + c\varkappa^{-2} 2\omega_0(2\omega_0 - ia) \\
 &\quad \left. + c^2 \varkappa^{-1} a(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) \right], \\
 H_3 &= i \left[2\theta_z - (-2a)^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) + a^{-1} - \omega_0 \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + ia(2c)^{-1} \right], \\
 H_4 &= -\frac{1}{2} \left(2(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) + \frac{1}{2}\theta_z \right)^2 \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left(2a^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) - \frac{1}{2}\theta_z \right) \theta_z - c^{-1}\theta_z^2 \\
 &\quad + \left(p_0 \exp(i\Omega_0)^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) + 2\omega_0(2a^{-1}(\theta_\omega \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \Omega_0) - \frac{1}{2}\theta_z) \right) + 2ic^{-1}(\theta_\omega - \Omega_0) \\
 &\quad + ia(2c)^{-1}\theta_z + 2d_1 p_0^{-1}, \\
 \beta &= b_1 + i\omega_0 b_2 - \omega_0^2 b_3 - i\omega_0^3 b_4.
 \end{aligned}$$

Recall that θ_z takes the value of 0 or 1/2 if N is even or odd, respectively.

Summarizing, the boundary value problem (59), (60), (63) plays the role of a quasinormal form for the boundary value problem (11), (12) in the critical case under consideration.

6. Conclusion

In this article we have proposed the integro-differential boundary value problem (11), (12) in order to model the dynamics of chains of a large number of oscillators with delayed advective couplings. The delay in the coupling lines has been also assumed to be large. The local analysis of this problem has been presented in the neighborhood of zero equilibrium state.

We have shown that when the equilibrium becomes unstable, an asymptotically (at $N^{-1}, T^{-1} \rightarrow 0$) infinite numbers of wave modes are excited. The assumption $T \gg 1$

allows us to obtain the explicit formulas for all critical parameters. We have found that such infinite-dimensional critical cases differ for bi- or unidirectional couplings, weak or strong dissipation of the oscillators, for distributed or discrete couplings, for odd or even numbers of the oscillators.

We have derived quasinormal forms, which turned out to be nonlinear boundary value problems of the parabolic type containing no small parameters, in each critical case mentioned above. The nonlocal dynamics of the quasinormal form, which can be rather complex (see, for example, [29]), determines the local behavior of the solutions of the original nonlinear problem. Asymptotic series for the nonlinear solutions can be obtained with the required accuracy on an infinite time interval using the main terms determined as the solutions of the corresponding quasinormal form. The coefficients of the quasinormal forms obtained through the original parameters of a chain allow us to study further the dependence of the dynamics on the delay T in coupling lines and the dissipation coefficient a of the oscillators.

The dynamics of chains with bi- or unidirectional couplings is specified by the function $\Phi_1(s)$ or $\Phi_2(s)$ in the original model. Corresponding quasinormal forms differ in the number of equations, coefficients and boundary conditions.

Dissipation of oscillators plays an important role in the dynamics. The structure of solutions can be more complicated in the case of weak dissipation $a^2 < 2$ rather than in the case of strong dissipation $a^2 > 2$. If $a^2 < 2$, the solutions contain a rapidly oscillating carrier component while the dynamics of the amplitude envelope is described by the quasinormal forms of the Ginzburg – Landau type.

Although quasinormal forms do not explicitly contain the small parameter $\varepsilon \sim N^{-1}$, but they depend essentially on ε through the parameters θ_ω and θ_z . As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, both parameters run through 0 to $c\omega_0$ and from 0 to 1, respectively, unlimited numbers of times.

That can lead to alternations of forward and backward bifurcations in quasilinear forms [30]. In this way we indicate the high sensitivity of the dynamical properties to the changes in the parameter ε , and hence to the changes in the values of N and T .

The cases of distributed or discrete couplings specified by the parameter σ have been considered. It has been shown that the quasilinear forms at small enough $\sigma \ll 1$ includes the diffusion operator for three spatial variables. That manifests the complex dynamics of the initial problem.

The results obtained admit an extension to other systems with advective and other couplings (see, e.g., [13–15]) and open a way for further studying of the complex dynamics of the oscillator chains.

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